

Table S1 Correlation between PDRG1 and TMB.

Cancer types	Correlation coefficient	<i>P</i> value
PAAD	0.312	6.20E-05
LGG	0.283	1.18E-10
SARC	0.269	4.17E-05
LUAD	0.258	4.73E-09
LUSC	0.209	5.67E-06
BLCA	0.207	3.02E-05
STAD	0.175	0.000773483
SKCM	0.122	0.00839396
LIHC	0.112	0.047673238
THCA	-0.168	0.000216704
UVM	-0.226	0.043986586
THYM	-0.272	0.003092535
COAD	-0.334	1.82E-10
MESO	0.218	0.050821827
KICH	0.11	0.383852315
GBM	0.102	0.217698652
TGCT	0.092	0.302571841
ACC	0.087	0.446351022
ESCA	0.079	0.329902078
HNSC	0.074	0.101206986
CESC	0.051	0.539760994
PRAD	0.051	0.262138891
DLBC	0.036	0.8320026
LAML	0.026	0.793958061
BRCA	0.013	0.685709522
OV	-0.003	0.959690779
READ	-0.036	0.69303632
CHOL	-0.037	0.832713171
KIRP	-0.041	0.501685578
KIRC	-0.044	0.413539133
UCEC	-0.055	0.213565093
PCPG	-0.098	0.19479388
UCS	-0.24	0.072041706

Table S2 Correlation between PDRG1 and MSI.

Cancer types	Correlation coefficient	<i>P</i> value
DLBC	0.447	0.00143187
KICH	0.355	0.0036958
KIRC	0.276	2.55E-07
ACC	0.238	0.03484629
BLCA	0.162	0.0010624
SARC	0.144	0.02209652
LIHC	0.118	0.02307427
PCPG	-0.161	0.02997027
COAD	-0.171	0.00039809
CHOL	0.172	0.32105645
TGCT	0.155	0.0732781
PAAD	0.132	0.07969949
KIRP	0.099	0.09299945
ESCA	0.076	0.33577851
THYM	0.076	0.41403641
STAD	0.065	0.20993789
UCS	0.062	0.64752847
UCEC	0.058	0.17595713
PRAD	0.054	0.23188782
LUSC	0.037	0.40880763
HNSC	0.026	0.56010024
MESO	0.019	0.86508855
UVM	0.018	0.87250638
BRCA	0.007	0.82384395
LUAD	0.006	0.88951127
SKCM	-0.008	0.8553347
OV	-0.009	0.877317
THCA	-0.02	0.66027648
LGG	-0.026	0.5643934
READ	-0.046	0.57459993
CESC	-0.054	0.35210035
LAML	-0.103	0.27439981
GBM	-0.113	0.16782712